

BIOPOLE Newsletter

Summer 2023

compiled by Ruta Hamilton (BAS)

Welcome to our seasonal newsletter!

BIOPOLE Arctic fieldwork is now well under way. In the waters to the west of Svalbard, Katrin Linse and Jennifer Freer (BAS) took part in a cruise on *RV Polarstern* to carry out open-ocean sampling for deep living copepods and the benthic animals that might feed on them. They came home blessed with samples on which to perform further morphometric and biochemical analyses.

Alanna Grant and Nathan Callaghan (UKCEH) are presently on Svalbard itself, at the British Arctic base in Ny Ålesund. Alanna and Nathan are collecting terrestrial and glacial samples. With a week to go of their month long trip, they still have much to do but have already secured an impressive number of samples. By coincidence, their stay overlapped with that of the poet laureate Simon Armitage, who visited to see the amazing Arctic landscape and witness rapid environmental change first hand. Maybe BIOPOLE will feature in one of his next poems...

BIOPOLE has also been busy on the influencing front, with Andy Shepherd (CPOM) and myself going to the Houses of Parliament to give evidence to an All-

Party Parliamentary Group on the status of UK scientific research in the Arctic. Also, in anticipation the first BIOPOLE cruise to the Southern Ocean in November and December this year, Nadine Johnston (BAS) guided a number of journalists around the RRS Sir David Attenborough (SDA) whilst it was in Scotland. The media visit resulted in articles in the Times, New Scientist and the Carbon Brief amongst others. Andrew Meijers (BAS), who will lead the cruise, will in fact be in charge of the first science project to be carried out on the SDA.

In addition to these stories, please read on to find out how to get involved in the BIOPOLE mentoring scheme and to learn more about star data manager, Petra ten Hoopen.

Geraint Tarling (Principal Investigator)

Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) "Navigating Gender at Sea"

On 18 May 2023, the BIOPOLE project member [Dani Jones](#) from [British Antarctic Survey](#) presented their co-authored article "Navigating Gender at Sea" to the BIOPOLE Executive Board. Dani discussed obstacles faced by the transgender and gender diverse scientists on fieldwork and offered some advice of how to make seagoing work safer for these communities.

[Read the article](#)

AGU Advances

COMMENTARY
10.1029/2023AV000927

Peer Review The peer review history for this article is available as a PDF in the Supporting Information.

Key Points:

- Limited attention has been given to the challenges faced by transgender and gender diverse (TGD) scientists
- TGD people face harassment, gendered berthing, and other legal and physical barriers while working at sea
- Improvements to increase equity can be made at the individual, chief scientist and officer, and institutional levels

Supporting Information:
Supporting Information may be found in the online version of this article.

Correspondence to:
K. McMonigal,
kmcmonigal@alaska.edu

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Navigating Gender at Sea

Kay McMonigal^{1,2}, **Natalya Evans**³, **Dani Jones**⁴, **Jay Brett**⁵, **Reece C. James**⁶, **Mar C. Arroyo**⁷, **A-bel Y. Gong**⁸, **Elizabeth C. Miller**⁶, **Colette Kelly**⁹, **Jule Middleton**³, **Chris Spear**¹⁰, **Wil Holmes**, and **Dakota Lane**¹¹

¹Department of Marine, Earth, and Atmospheric Sciences, North Carolina State University, Raleigh, NC, USA, ²Now at College of Fisheries and Ocean Sciences, University of Alaska Fairbanks, Fairbanks, AK, USA, ³Marine Science Institute, University of California Santa Barbara, Santa Barbara, CA, USA, ⁴British Antarctic Survey, NERC, UKRI, Cambridge, UK, ⁵Johns Hopkins University Applied Physics Laboratory, Laurel, MD, USA, ⁶Department of Oceanography, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa, Honolulu, HI, USA, ⁷Department of Ocean Sciences, University of California Santa Cruz, Santa Cruz, CA, USA, ⁸University of San Diego, San Diego, CA, USA, ⁹Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, Woods Hole, MA, USA, ¹⁰University of Chicago, Chicago, IL, USA, ¹¹Loyola University Chicago, Chicago, IL, USA

Abstract Fieldwork, including work done at sea, is a key component of many geoscientists' careers. Recent studies have highlighted the pervasive harassment faced by women and LGBTQ+ people during fieldwork. However, transgender and gender diverse (TGD) scientists face obstacles which have not yet been thoroughly examined. We fill this gap by sharing our experiences as TGD people. We have experienced sexual harassment, misconduct, privacy issues, and legal and medical struggles as we conduct seagoing work. In this work, we provide recommendations for individuals, cruise leaders, and institutions for making seagoing work safer for our communities.

Plain Language Summary Transgender and gender diverse people have unique lived experiences. Work done in the field and at sea are integral components of many geoscientists' careers. Understanding the barriers that transgender and gender diverse (TGD) people face during fieldwork is one facet of making the geoscience community more diverse, equitable, and welcoming. This commentary shares some of the lived experiences of the authors and provides recommendations for making seagoing work more welcoming to TGD people.

McMonigal, K., Evans, N., Jones, D., Brett, J., James, R. C., Arroyo, M. C., et al. (2023). Navigating gender at sea. *AGU Advances*, 4, e2023AV000927. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023AV000927>

Launching the BIOPOLE Mentoring Scheme

The BIOPOLE mentoring scheme is ready to launch and aims to support BIOPOLE's Early Career Researchers (ECRs) with their academic progression and/or professional development.

The BIOPOLE mentoring scheme is open to all BIOPOLE's ECRs (self-defining) and will be coordinated by the BIOPOLE ECR network and the Executive Board. We are very keen to engage BIOPOLE stakeholders in the mentoring scheme, both to act as mentors or for stakeholders ECRs to engage as a mentee. We are also in the process of connecting to other broader mentoring schemes – watch this space!

If you would like to sign up as a mentor or mentee or are having issues viewing the BIOPOLE mentoring scheme documents please get in touch with the BIOPOLE ECR representative (2023-24) [Chelsey Baker](mailto:chelsey.baker@noc.ac.uk) at chelsey.baker@noc.ac.uk.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

BIOPOLE POLAR ECOSYSTEMS GLOBAL IMPACTS | BIOPOLE Mentoring: Getting Started

Please fill out in first mentoring meeting, and upload to BIOPOLE [Sharepoint](#)

Mentor/Mentee Details

	Name	Institution	Email Address	Date
Mentor				
Mentee				

Meetings

How will you be conducting the mentoring? (In-person, virtually)

How often are you planning to meet?

How long will the formal duration of mentoring be?

Mentoring Aims

Please outline any aims or goals you would like to achieve through BIOPOLE mentoring.

Example of the mentoring 'getting started' form that should be completed during the first mentor-mentee meeting

BIOPOLE in Parliament

On 12 June 2023, BIOPOLE's [Geraint Tarling](#) and [Andy Shepherd](#) gave evidence at a hearing called by the All-party Parliamentary Polar Research Sub-Committee exploring UK's relationship to the Arctic environment. This parliamentary committee is considering the UK's contribution to the Arctic through scientific research.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

Geraint Tarling and Andy Shepherd providing evidence to the All-party Parliamentary Polar Research Sub-Committee

Team BIOPOLE in the Arctic

Since 1999, the [Alfred-Wegener Institute](#) (AWI), has conducted long-term ecological research in the Fram Strait, the passage between East Greenland and Svalbard. In June, [Katrin Linse](#) and [Jen Freer](#) joined for this year's 'HAUSGARTEN' expedition on board the research vessel and icebreaker, **Polarstern**.

This was a fantastic opportunity to collect data with BIOPOLE project partners from AWI ([Barbara Niehoff](#) and [Sinhué Torres-Valdes](#)) and the [Senckenberg Institute](#) ([Saskia Brix](#)) which would span the breadth of BIOPOLE's aims: to understand how nutrients and ecosystems in polar environments influence global primary productivity and carbon cycling from the surface to the seafloor.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

A birds-eye view of the Polarstern during the HAUSGARTEN expedition.

Credit: Jonas Hagemann

Feature on Petra ten Hoopen Data Management Lead

Petra: 'I am a Scientific Data Manager at the UK Polar Data Centre at the British Antarctic Survey. Before joining BAS, I have spent ten years in fundamental science working in several countries on plant hormonal pathways and stress response and then moved to a data-focussed profession. For the last ten years I work with marine data, specifically genomic data at EMBL-EBI and environmental data at BAS. In my current role, I archive, publish and integrate UK-funded polar marine data, develop databases, collaborate with other data professionals on developing the data publishing infrastructure and engage with national and international communities, such as the NERC Environmental Data Service, Southern Ocean Observing System, Polar Data Forum or Research Data Alliance.'

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

RRS Sir David Attenborough Sea Trials and Media Trip

In early July the *RRS Sir David Attenborough* set sail from Edinburgh to the North Sea to conduct sea trials ahead of its maiden science cruise in Nov-Dec: BIOPOLE Southern Ocean Cruise 1 which will be led by Andrew Meijers! Hugh Venables (BAS) is part of the trials team for its duration (until mid-August), providing expertise on the CTDs and autonomous platforms (including gliders). Nadine Johnston (BAS) also joined for the first few days of the trials, taking the opportunity to step through some net deployment logistics (to collect zooplankton), including deployment of the mammoth net (which will be trialed through the ship's 'moonpool').

Coverage by the media (including BIOPOLE) include articles in [Carbon Brief](#), [The Times](#) and [New Scientist](#) (these are both behind a paywall so see figures below), and [Shipping Technology Magazine](#). There is also a New Scientist video on [You Tube](#). Many thanks to everyone involved, great to see the BIOPOLE flag flying!

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

Modern-day Shackletons all set for a smashing time in Antarctic

The research vessel, which boasts a gym and a bar, is being prepared for its maiden scientific mission. Below: Captain Will Whitley

Rhys Blakely chills out aboard the RRS Sir David Attenborough (otherwise not known as Boaty McBoatface)

Captain Will Whitley doesn't hesitate when he's asked to name the best part of his job. "There is nothing as much fun," he says, "as taking a brand new ice-breaker to the Antarctic."

While most mariners will do their utmost to avoid striking ice, Whitley's role involves seeking it out and carving through it. As master of the RRS Sir David Attenborough, he's in charge of one of the world's most sophisticated polar science vessels — a £200 million, state-of-the-art floating research station designed to navigate some of the most dangerous environments on the planet and unlock their mysteries.

Operated by the British Antarctic Survey (BAS), it has been built to crunch through sea ice metres thick, to gather data from miles beneath the ocean surface, and to transport people and supplies to five remote research stations around the South Pole. Measuring 129 metres from bow to stern, it can accommodate 30 crew and 60 scientists. There are 14 laboratories — a dramatic upgrade on its predecessor, the RRS James Clark Ross, which had only two. While still under construction, it won renown as the public voted to call it "Boaty McBoatface" — a name vetoed by ministers and given instead to a small robotic underwater vehicle.

And this week, as it underwent sea trials off the coast of Scotland in preparation for its maiden scientific mission, The Times became the first media organisation to travel on board.

There is an apocryphal tale of the explorer Sir Ernest Shackleton placing a job advert in this newspaper a century ago. "Men wanted for hazardous journey," it supposedly said. "Low wages, bitter cold, long hours of complete

darkness. Safe return doubtful. Honour and recognition in event of success."

For those who work on the Attenborough, the thrill of travelling to the ends of the Earth still helps to compensate for modest salaries. But the privations of 19th and 20th-century expeditions are a thing of the past. The creature comforts include a sauna and gym, a decently stocked bar, and fancy dress parties. The food is excellent. The ships can carry more than three tonnes of flour, with bread baked daily. There are fish and chips every Friday. There is little chance of having to resort to penguins and seals, as past explorers did.

But there are also reminders that Attenborough operates in dangerous waters, including a room where enough polar clothing, tents and survival supplies are kept to keep 90 people alive on the ice for three weeks should disaster strike. During trials in the Southern Ocean, the Attenborough has already seen brutal weather. Crossing the Drake Passage, which separates Cape Horn in South America and Antarctica, towards the Falklands this year, it was caught in a storm that measured 11 on the Beaufort scale, which only goes up to 12. The waves were between 8 and 10m high and the winds approached 100mph. It lasted 36 hours. "It was pretty bumpy — you wouldn't want it every day," said Rob Bellis, chief officer. "But you know the ship can deal with it. You know the people on board are trained to deal with it. And that gives you a warm fuzzy feeling. The scariest thing is getting your lunch — best to avoid the soup on a force 11 day."

The ship made history last year, with two of its crew — Eric Bouaine, a steward, and Stephen Carpenter, a cook — becoming the first same-sex couple to be married in the Antarctic, with Cap-

tain Whitley officiating. This week, the seas off Scotland were calm. Near Arbroath, the Attenborough's engine room whirred into life as its "dynamic positioning system" — which uses four thrusters and the ship's two propellers to keep the vessel fixed on a certain location — was tested.

Ready to explore

tain Whitley officiating. This week, the seas off Scotland were calm. Near Arbroath, the Attenborough's engine room whirred into life as its "dynamic positioning system" — which uses four thrusters and the ship's two propellers to keep the vessel fixed on a certain location — was tested.

It is the first British polar research ship to feature a "moon pool" — a vertical shaft, about 4m by 4m, that runs through the vessel, open to the sea below. It allows scientific equipment to be deployed and recovered through the central, most stable section of the hull, even when ice on either side stops them from using the ship's cranes. It was used for the first time this week, to lower one of the ship's remotely operated vehicles, a small underwater robot fitted with cameras, into the water. The crew also test-

ed a new fuel — hydrotreated vegetable oil, sometimes known as renewable diesel — for the first time. It could potentially cut the carbon emissions of the four Rolls-Royce engines by as much as 95 per cent.

All of this was preparation for the Attenborough's first full science mission, called Biopole. Due to begin this year, it will seek to unravel one of the most important — and least understood — ecological processes on the planet. The sea ice that forms in Antarctica each winter contains vast amounts of phosphorus and nitrogen, picked up from the continent itself by the winds. This helps to trigger a massive phytoplankton bloom — an explosion of microscopic marine life that converts sunlight and CO2 into food and oxygen on an epic scale. Without this annual burst of "primary production" at the bottom of the world, ocean life would not exist as

we know it. Fisheries in the middle latitudes depend on it: economies are built on it. And scientists fear that if climate change spells the end of the sea ice, this ecological pillar will vanish.

Dr Nadine Johnston of BAS will be one of a dozen scientists who will use the Attenborough to study the process in unprecedented detail. Part of the work will focus on copepods — tiny creatures that gorge on phytoplankton to fatten themselves, building up a supply of fatty lipids. When winter comes, they sink down into the deep ocean, carrying their carbon-rich lipid supplies with them. It can stay down there for centuries. By some estimates, the mass of copepods in the oceans is ten times that of all the humans on land. Yet their life cycle is poorly understood.

The object, Johnston explains, is to understand these processes, well enough to be able to predict how climate change is likely to affect them. The ultimate aim is to inform policy at the highest levels and BAS has a track record of influence. The hole in the ozone layer was discovered in Antarctica in 1985 by one of its junior researchers. It led to the Montreal Protocol and the banning of CFCs — an example of international co-operation averting an environmental disaster.

First, though, it will have to negotiate the same frozen ocean that crushed Shackleton's *Endurance* in 1915. Captain Whitley explains that the ship doesn't cut directly into the ice; it meets, like an axe. Rather, the front of the vessel is designed to rise up on to it. It will crush through it as it falls.

If the ice has somewhere to go, the ship can push it out of the way. If it's fixed in place, pinned in by surrounding land, it's a far tougher obstacle. If the ice is also covered in lots of snow, it becomes even more difficult.

Whitley once covered just 20 miles in two weeks. Asked what attributes an icebreaker captain needs, he said: "Patience." But he sounded eager to head south. "To see a ship like this in her home environment — I can't think of anything more exciting," he said.

'The Times' article

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News

Field notes The North Sea

RRS Sir David Attenborough gears up for Antarctica State-of-the-art equipment on the polar research ship is being tested in the North Sea before its first science voyage. **Alec Luhn** joins the crew

ON THE Antarctic research ship Sir David Attenborough, engineers are gathered around a 4-metre square opening in the hull, known as the moon pool. A white robot floats in the water, its headlights illuminating the sides of the pool.

"Now push it forward and drop it to the bottom," says Jamie Neilson, an engineering supervisor at Seatronics, the maker of this remotely operated vehicle.

With a press of a joystick, the thrusters whirr into life and the robot disappears beneath a spurt of bubbles. Its job is to scour the hull of the ship for damage or invasive species and perform tasks with its controllable arms, like installing cameras on the bottom of an Antarctic ice shelf.

This isn't Antarctica, however, but the North Sea, where the Attenborough is testing key equipment before its maiden science voyage to the Southern Ocean. Though the ship has been on the water for two seasons, bringing supplies to research bases and undergoing polar sea trials, this November it will finally start doing real research in Antarctica.

"It's much better to spend a month now testing than to go all the way down south only to find out that there's actually a critical problem, and we can't deploy our instrumentation," says Carson McAfee, the ship's electronics engineer.

These sea trials, which begin with a safety announcement recorded by David Attenborough himself, are the first time that

The RRS Sir David Attenborough (top); a submersible robot in the ship's moon pool (left); engineers guiding the robot (right)

journalists have been on this ship at sea. As it leaves the Rosyth Dockyard near Edinburgh, UK, the Attenborough's diesel engines are burning hydrotreated vegetable oil, made of leftover cooking oil and animal fat. If that is successful, the British Antarctic Survey (BAS)

£200m

Cost of the RRS Sir David Attenborough

could decide to run the ship on this oil all the way to Antarctica, which would slash emissions by up to 95 per cent, but also double fuel costs.

The bright red vessel slowly navigates through a narrow lock and under three bridges. Its dynamic positioning system, a set of four thrusters that keep the ship

positioned exactly on a GPS coordinate or route, is also being tested in these trials.

The Attenborough is 129 metres long, weighs 15,000 tonnes and can break through ice more than 2 metres thick. With 12 decks, 13 laboratories and even an experimental aquarium, it has as much space for research as the entire BAS headquarters in Cambridge.

Its greatest strength, however, isn't its size, but its complexity. Scientists helped design the £200-million (\$258-million) vessel's state-of-the-art operational systems and research equipment. The next few months will test not only whether all that equipment works, but also whether the crew of 30 knows how to use it. In August, they will practise taking different sediment cores from the

deep seafloor between Shetland and the Faroe Islands.

"Once we start to go into full-capacity science on board, which we're doing this year, we're going to learn so much more about what it can do," says laboratory manager Aisling Smith.

Some of that science will be for the BIOPOLE programme, a £9-million project to study how the cycling of nutrients from the poles to the oceans is changing. Researchers are testing a rig of 12 electronically operated nets that will help them take samples of a type of zooplankton called a copepod in Antarctica this November.

Copepods are typically no bigger than a lentil, but they are so numerous that they collectively weigh 10 times more than all humans put together. They also have a big impact on the climate. When sea ice melts in spring, it sparks a phytoplankton bloom that absorbs carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. Copepods eat these phytoplankton, then sink to the sea floor, where the carbon can remain for centuries.

In this way, the tiny creatures sequester at least 1 billion tonnes of carbon per year. The fear is that, as Antarctic sea ice retreats, fewer nutrients will be available for phytoplankton and, in turn, copepods to grow.

"It's really important that we can understand just how much carbon [copepods] are capable of drawing down to depth," says ecologist Nadine Johnston at BAS. The moon pool will play a major role in that. "Normally, when we get to the sea ice, that's where our science kind of stops," says Johnston. "But because this ship has a moon pool, once we get down into the sea ice, we can gather data in places where we've never been able to get it before."

BIOPOLE Endorsed as a UN Decade Project

BIOPOLE has recently been formally endorsed as a UN Decade Project (Unique ID 25.3; Polar Ecosystems, Global Impacts (BIOPOLE)), hosted by the Joint Exploration of the Twilight Zone Ocean Network (JETZON).

[Read more on UN Ocean Decade website](#)

2021
2030 United Nations Decade
of Ocean Science
for Sustainable Development

For further information please visit the UN Ocean Decade [website](#).

Upcoming Relevant Events

The Bluedot Festival 2023

**20-23 July 2023 in Jodrell Bank Observatory,
Cheshire, UK, Earth**

For more information about the festival, [please click here](#)

SOOS Symposium

SOUTHERN OCEAN IN A CHANGING WORLD

**The first Southern Ocean Observing System
(SOOS) Symposium**

14-18 August 2023 in Hobart, Tasmania

**For more information about the symposium and to
register, [please click here](#)**

**The INStabilities & Thresholds in ANTarctica
(INSTANT) organised by the Scientific Committee
on Antarctic Research (SCAR)**

11-14 September 2023 in Trieste, Italy

**For more information about the conference and to
register, [please click here](#)**

